

Initial Teacher Education in Spain: An Assessment of Digital Competence for Teachers through the DigCompEdu Framework

Authors: Celia Moreno-Morilla, Jonatan Castaño-Muñoz y Eduardo García-Jiménez

Annex 1. Distribution of references by areas, competences and type of mention

1. PROFESSIONAL ENGAGEMENT	
1.1. Organisational communication	Use digital technologies to improve organisational communication with students, parents, and third parties. Contribute to developing and enhancing organisational communication strategies.
1.2. Professional collaboration	Use digital technologies to collaborate with other educators by sharing knowledge and experiences, and by collaboratively innovating pedagogical practices. Use professional collaborative networks as a source of professional development.
1.3. Reflective practice	Reflect on, critically evaluate, and actively develop one's own digital pedagogical practice and that of the educational community.
1.4. Continuous professional development	Use digital sources and resources for continuous professional development.

2. DIGITAL RESOURCES	
2.1. Selecting digital resources	Identify, evaluate, and select digital resources for teaching and learning; understand applicable copyright and accessibility requirements.
2.2. Creating and modifying digital resources	Modify existing open-licensed resources and other resources where permitted. Create or co-create new digital educational resources. Take into account the specific learning objective, context, pedagogical approach, and group of students when designing and planning the use of digital resources.
2.3. Managing, protecting, and sharing digital resources	Organise digital content and make it available to students, parents, or other educators. Effectively protect sensitive digital content. Respect privacy and copyright regulations. Understand the use and creation of open licences and Open Educational Resources (OER), including proper attribution.

3. TEACHING AND LEARNING	
3.1. Teaching	Integrate digital devices and resources into the teaching process to enhance the effectiveness of teaching practices. Properly adapt foundations, manage, and orchestrate digital teaching interventions. Experiment with and develop new pedagogical formats and methods of instruction.
3.2. Guidance	Use digital tools and services to enhance interaction with students, individually and collectively, both inside and outside the learning session. Use digital technologies to provide timely and specific guidance and support. Experiment with and develop new forms and formats of guidance and support.
3.3. Collaborative learning	Use digital technologies to foster and enhance collaborative learning strategies (e.g., as a basis for group exchange, as a tool for carrying out collaborative assignments, or as a means for presenting outcomes).
3.4. Self-regulated learning	Use digital technologies to support self-regulated learning processes, enabling students to plan, monitor, and reflect on their own learning, document progress, share knowledge, and present creative solutions.

4. ASSESSMENT AND FEEDBACK	
4.1. Assessment strategies	Use digital tools for formative and summative assessment. Enhance the diversity and appropriateness of assessment formats and approaches.
4.2. Analysing evidence	Generate, select, critically analyse, and interpret digital evidence of students' digital activity, performance, and progress to inform teaching and learning. Use digital tools to provide timely and targeted feedback to students. Properly adapt teaching strategies and provide guided support based on the evidence generated by digital tools.
4.3. Feedback and planning	Help students and parents understand the evidence provided by digital tools and use it for decision-making.

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5. EMPOWERING LEARNERS	
5.1. Accesibility and inclusion	Ensure accessibility to resources and learning activities for all students, including those with special needs. Consider and respond to students' digital expectations, skills, digital habits and misconceptions, as well as contextual, physical, or cognitive constraints affecting the use of digital tools.
5.2. Differentiation and personalisation	Use digital tools to address students' diverse learning needs (e.g., by allowing them to pursue different learning paths and goals, offering alternative approaches and tools, and enabling learners to progress at different paces toward individual learning objectives). Use digital tools to foster students' active and creative engagement with a subject.
5.3. Actively engaging learners	Use digital technologies to promote transversal competences and students' creative expression. Open learning to real-world contexts by engaging students in practical activities, scientific inquiry, complex problem-solving, and creative expression.

6. FACILITATING STUDENTS' DIGITAL COMPETENCE	
6.1. Information and media literacy	Incorporate learning activities, tasks, and assessments that require students to articulate information needs; locate information and resources in digital environments; organise, process, analyse, and interpret information; and critically compare and evaluate the credibility and reliability of information and its sources.
6.2. Digital communication and collaboration	Incorporate learning activities, tasks, and assessments that require students to effectively and responsibly use digital tools for communication, collaboration, and civic participation.
6.3. Digital content creation	Incorporate learning activities and assignments that require students to express themselves through digital media and to modify and create digital content in various formats. Teach students how copyright and licences apply to digital content, how to reference sources, and how to apply licences.
6.4. Responsible use	Take measures to ensure students' physical, psychological, and social wellbeing when using digital technologies. Empower students to manage risks and use digital technologies to support their own social, psychological, and physical wellbeing.
6.5. Digital problem solving	Incorporate learning activities and assessments that require students to identify and resolve technical problems or creatively transfer their technological knowledge to new situations.

7. DIFFERENTIATORS BY TYPE OF MENTION TO ICT	
7.1. Explicit	Direct and manifest references to the use of Information and Communication Technologies (ICT) in the competences included in the verification reports.
7.2. Implicit	Indirect references where the use of Information and Communication Technologies (ICT) can be assumed or inferred in the competences included in the verification reports.

8. DIFFERENTIATORS BY TYPE OF COMPETENCE	
8.1. Basic competences	Competence mentions appearing under the category of <i>basic competences</i> ¹ .
8.2. Transversal competences	Competence mentions appearing under the category of <i>transversal competences</i> ² .
8.3. General competences	Competence mentions appearing under the category of <i>general competences</i> ³ .
8.4. Specific competences	Competence mentions appearing under the category of <i>specific competences</i> ⁴ .

¹Basic Competences: common to all degrees at the same MECES level (Spanish Qualifications Framework for Higher Education), established by RD 861/2010 and differentiated for bachelor's and master's degrees.

²Transversal Competences: common to all degrees within the same university.

³General Competences: common to all degrees within a university but adapted to the specific context of each programme.

⁴Specific Competences: unique to each degree, aimed at achieving the specific graduate profile.

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Annex 2. Comparison of references by type of degree and mention

Competence	Degree	Explicit	Implicit	Explicit + Implicit
Professional engagement	ECE vs PE	z=0.16 p=.873	z=3.06 p<.01	z=3.31 p<.01
	ECE vs. MTT	z=1.60 p=.110	z=3.06 p<.01	z=3.32 p<.01
	PE vs. MTT	z= 1.46 p=.144	z=0.00 p=1.00	z=-1.01 p=.313
Digital resources	ECE vs PE	z=-2.34 p<.05	z=1.69 p=.091	z=-1.38 p=.168
	ECE vs. MTT	z=-3.24 p<.01	z=0.65 p=.516	z=-3.06 p<.01
	PE vs. MTT	z=-4.52 p<.01	z=-1.30 p=.194	z=-1.89 p=.059
Teaching and learning	ECE vs PE	z=1.39 p=.177	z=-2.37 p<.05	z=-1.01 p=.313
	ECE vs. MTT	z=-3.75 p<.01	z=-2.49 p<.05	z=-4.17 p<.01
	PE vs. MTT	z=-4.38 p<.01	z=-0.13 p=.897	z=-3.32 p<.01
Assessment	ECE vs PE	z=2.15 p<.05	z=-2.33 p<.05	z=-1.05 p=.294
	ECE vs. MTT	z=2.29 p<.05	z=6.45 p<.01	z=3.22 p<.01
	PE vs. MTT	z=0.51 p=.610	z=8.88 p<.01	z=3.74 p<.01
Empowering learners	ECE vs PE	z=1.13 p=.026	z=-0.68 p=.497	z=1.25 p=.211
	ECE vs. MTT	z=1.34 p=.180	z=1.25 p=.211	z=2.26 p<.05
	PE vs. MTT	z=-0.24 p=.810	z=1.75 p=.080	z=1.37 p=.171
Facilitating Learners' Digital Competence	ECE vs PE	z=-2.55 p<.05	z=-0.23 p=.818	z=-2.48 p<.05
	ECE vs. MTT	z=1.55 p=.121	z=-0.23 p=.818	z=1.93 p=.054
	PE vs. MTT	z=2.45 p<.05	z=0.00 p=1.000	z=3.08 p<.01
TOTAL	ECE vs PE	z=-0.25 p=.803	z=-1.07 p=.285	z=-1.04 p=.299
	ECE vs. MTT	z=-0.60 p=.549	z=2.30 p<.05	z=1.30 p=.194
	PE vs. MTT	z=-0.20 p=.842	z=3.31 p<.01	z=2.33 p<.05

Annex 3. Analysis by type of competence, mention and degree

3.1. Explicit mentions

		EXPLICIT MENTIONS														
Dimension	Competences	n	COMPETENCE TYPE						DEGREE							
			B		T		G		S		ECE		PE		MTT	
		n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%	
Professional Engagement	Organisational communication	25	0	0.0	12	48.0	3	12.0	10	40.0	8	32.0	12	48.0	5	20.0
	Professional collaboration	24	0	0.0	4	16.7	7	29.2	13	54.2	4	16.7	7	29.2	13	54.2
	Reflective practice	28	0	0.0	25	89.3	3	10.7	0	0.0	16	57.1	1	3.6	11	39.3
	Digital Continuous Professional Development	57	0	0.0	31	54.4	26	45.6	0	0.0	25	43.9	31	54.4	1	1.8
	TOTAL AREA	134	0	0.0	72	53.7	39	29.1	23	17.2	53	39.6	51	38.1	30	22.4
Digital Resources	Selecting digital resources	184	0	0.0	11	6.0	116	63.0	57	31.0	26	14.1	68	37.0	90	48.9
	Creating and modifying digital content	28	0	0.0	2	7.1	12	42.9	14	50.0	7	25.0	11	39.3	10	35.7
	Managing, protecting and sharing digital resources	3	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0	3	100	0	0.0	2	66.7	1	33.3
	TOTAL AREA	215	0	0.0	13	6.0	128	59.5	74	34.4	33	15.3	81	37.7	101	47.0
Teaching and Learning	Teaching	229	0	0.0	5	2.2	76	33.2	148	64.6	65	28.4	37	16.2	127	55.5
	Guidance	8	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0	8	100	0	0.0	0	0.0	8	100
	Collaborative learning	5	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0	5	100	2	40.0	3	60.0	0	0.0
	Self-regulated learning	5	0	0.0	0	0.0	2	40.0	3	60.0	2	40.0	1	20.0	2	40.0
	TOTAL AREA	247	0	0.0	5	2.0	78	31.6	164	66.4	69	27.9	41	16.6	137	55.5
Assessment	Assessment strategies	4	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0	4	100	2	50.0	1	25.0	1	25.0
	Analysing evidence	51	0	0.0	4	7.8	18	35.3	29	56.9	30	58.8	12	23.5	9	17.6
	Feedback and planning	2	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0	2	100	1	50.0	1	50.0	0	0.0
	TOTAL AREA	57	0	0.0	4	7.0	18	31.6	35	61.4	33	57.9	14	24.6	10	17.5
Empowering Learners	Accessibility and inclusion	2	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0	2	100	0	0.0	1	50.0	1	50.0
	Differentiation and personalisation	1	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0	1	100	0	0.0	0	0.0	1	100
	Actively engaging learners	21	0	0.0	0	0.0	1	4.8	20	95.2	20	95.2	0	0.0	1	4.8
	TOTAL AREA	24	0	0.0	0	0.0	1	4.2	23	95.8	20	83.3	1	4.2	3	12.5
Facilitating Learners' Digital Competence	Information and media literacy	4	0	0.0	0	0.0	2	50.0	2	50.0	4	100	0	0.0	0	0.0
	Digital communication and collaboration	1	0	0.0	1	100	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0	1	100
	Digital content creation	1	0	0.0	0	0.0	1	100	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0	1	100
	Responsible use	142	0	0.0	3	2.1	21	14.8	118	83.1	51	35.9	88	62.0	3	2.1
	Digital problem solving	6	0	0.0	0	0.0	3	50.0	3	50.0	3	50.0	3	50.0	0	0.0
	TOTAL AREA	154	0	0.0	4	2.6	27	17.5	123	79.9	58	37.7	91	59.1	5	3.2
TOTAL		831	0	0.0	98	11.8	291	0.4	442	53.2	266	32.0	279	33.6	286	34.4

3.2. Implicit mentions

IMPLICIT MENTIONS																
Dimension	Competences	n	COMPETENCE TYPE								DEGREE					
			B		T		G		S		ECE		PE		MTT	
			n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%
Professional Engagement	Organisational communication	39	0	0.0	0	0.0	6	15.4	33	84.6	27	69.2	1	2.6	11	28.2
	Professional collaboration	5	0	0.0	0	0.0	2	40.0	3	60.0	3	60.0	2	40.0	0	0.0
	Reflective practice	86	0	0.0	4	4.7	27	31.4	55	64.0	48	55.8	30	34.9	8	9.3
	Digital Continuous Professional Development	25	0	0.0	2	8.0	4	16.0	19	76.0	5	20.0	3	12.0	17	68.0
	TOTAL AREA	155	0	0.0	6	3.9	39	25.2	110	71.0	83	53.5	36	23.2	36	23.2
Digital Resources	Selecting digital resources	44	0	0.0	2	4.5	15	34.1	27	61.4	26	59.1	6	13.6	12	27.3
	Creating and modifying digital content	9	0	0.0	1	11.1	1	11.1	7	77.8	0	0.0	0	0.0	9	100
	Managing, protecting and sharing digital resources	0	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0
	TOTAL AREA	53	0	0.0	3	5.7	16	30.2	34	64.2	26	49.1	6	11.3	21	39.6
Teaching and Learning	Teaching	172	0	0.0	4	2.3	38	22.1	130	75.6	31	18.0	61	35.5	80	46.5
	Guidance	29	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0	29	100	0	0.0	0	0.0	29	100
	Collaborative learning	46	0	0.0	0	0.0	18	39.1	28	60.9	19	41.3	27	58.7	0	0.0
	Self-regulated learning	179	118	65.9	3	1.7	21	11.7	37	20.7	51	28.5	73	40.8	55	30.7
	TOTAL AREA	426	118	27.7	7	1.6	77	18.1	224	52.6	101	23.7	161	37.8	164	38.5
Assessment	Assessment strategies	87	0	0.0	1	1.1	5	5.7	81	93.1	26	29.9	57	65.5	4	4.6
	Analysing evidence	155	63	40.6	13	8.4	23	14.8	56	36.1	69	44.5	77	49.7	9	5.8
	Feedback and planning	1	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0	1	100	1	100	0	0.0	0	0.0
	TOTAL AREA	243	63	25.9	14	5.8	28	11.5	138	56.8	96	39.5	134	55.1	13	5.3
Empowering Learners	Accessibility and inclusion	35	0	0.0	0	0.0	3	8.6	32	91.4	24	68.6	4	11.4	7	20.0
	Differentiation and personalisation	6	0	0.0	0	0.0	1	16.7	5	83.3	1	16.7	1	16.7	4	66.7
	Actively engaging learners	26	0	0.0	1	3.8	2	7.7	23	88.5	0	0.0	26	100	0	0.0
	TOTAL AREA	67	0	0.0	1	1.5	6	9.0	60	89.6	25	37.3	31	46.3	11	16.4
Facilitating Learners' Digital Competence	Information and media literacy	1	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0	1	100	0	0.0	0	0.0	1	100
	Digital communication and collaboration	0	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0
	Digital content creation	1	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0	1	100	0	0.0	0	0.0	1	100
	Responsible use	3	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0	3	100	1	33.3	2	66.7	0	0.0
	Digital problem solving	9	0	0.0	3	33.3	6	66.7	0	0.0	3	33.3	3	33.3	3	33.3
	TOTAL AREA	14	0	0.0	3	21.4	6	42.9	5	35.7	4	28.6	5	35.7	5	35.7
TOTAL		958	181	18.9	34	3.5	172	18.0	571	59.6	335	35.0	373	38.9	250	26.1

3.3. Combined analysis (explicit + implicit)

COMBINED ANALYSIS (EXPLICIT + IMPLICIT)																
Dimension	Competences	n	COMPETENCE TYPE								DEGREE					
			B		T		G		S		ECE		PE		MTT	
			n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%
Professional Engagement	Organisational communication	64	0	0.0	12	18.8	9	14.1	43	67.2	35	54.7	13	20.3	16	25.0
	Professional collaboration	29	0	0.0	4	13.8	9	31.0	16	55.2	7	24.1	9	31.0	13	44.8
	Reflective practice	114	0	0.0	29	25.4	30	26.3	55	48.2	64	56.1	31	27.2	19	16.7
	Digital Continuous Professional Development	82	0	0.0	33	40.2	30	36.6	19	23.2	30	36.6	34	41.5	18	22.0
	TOTAL AREA	289	0	0.0	78	27.0	78	27.0	133	46.0	136	47.1	87	30.1	66	22.8
Digital Resources	Selecting digital resources	228	0	0.0	13	5.7	131	57.5	84	36.8	52	22.8	74	32.5	102	44.7
	Creating and modifying digital content	37	0	0.0	3	8.1	13	35.1	21	56.8	7	18.9	11	29.7	19	51.4
	Managing, protecting and sharing digital resources	3	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0	3	100	0	0.0	2	66.7	1	33.3
	TOTAL AREA	268	0	0.0	16	6.0	144	53.7	108	40.3	59	22.0	87	32.5	122	45.5
Teaching and Learning	Teaching	401	0	0.0	9	2.2	114	28.4	278	69.3	96	23.9	98	24.4	207	51.6
	Guidance	37	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0	37	100	0	0.0	0	0.0	37	100
	Collaborative learning	51	0	0.0	0	0.0	18	35.3	33	64.7	21	41.2	30	58.8	0	0.0
	Self-regulated learning	184	118	64.1	3	1.6	23	12.5	40	21.7	53	28.8	74	40.2	57	31.0
	TOTAL AREA	673	118	17.5	12	1.8	155	23.0	388	57.7	170	25.3	202	30.0	301	44.7
Assessment	Assessment strategies	91	0	0.0	1	1.1	5	5.5	85	93.4	28	30.8	58	63.7	5	5.5
	Analysing evidence	206	63	30.6	17	8.3	41	19.9	85	41.3	99	48.1	89	43.2	18	8.7
	Feedback and planning	3	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0	3	100	2	66.7	1	33.3	0	0.0
	TOTAL AREA	300	63	21.0	18	6.0	46	15.3	173	57.7	129	43.0	148	49.3	23	7.7
Empowering Learners	Accessibility and inclusion	37	0	0.0	0	0.0	3	8.1	34	91.9	24	64.9	5	13.5	8	21.6
	Differentiation and personalisation	7	0	0.0	0	0.0	1	14.3	6	85.7	1	14.3	1	14.3	5	71.4
	Actively engaging learners	47	0	0.0	1	2.1	3	6.4	43	91.5	20	42.6	26	55.3	1	2.1
	TOTAL AREA	91	0	0.0	1	1.1	7	7.7	83	91.2	45	49.5	32	35.2	14	15.4
Facilitating Learners' Digital Competence	Information and media literacy	5	0	0.0	0	0.0	2	40.0	3	60.0	4	80.0	0	0.0	1	20.0
	Digital communication and collaboration	1	0	0.0	1	100	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0	1	100
	Digital content creation	2	0	0.0	0	0.0	1	50.0	1	50.0	0	0.0	0	0.0	2	100
	Responsible use	145	0	0.0	3	2.1	21	14.5	121	83.4	52	35.9	90	62.1	3	2.1
	Digital problem solving	15	0	0.0	3	20.0	9	60.0	3	20.0	6	40.0	6	40.0	3	20.0
	TOTAL AREA	168	0	0.0	7	4.2	33	19.6	128	76.2	62	36.9	96	57.1	10	6.0
TOTAL		1789	181	10.1	132	0.1	463	25.9	1013	56.6	601	33.6	652	36.4	536	30.0